

LIVING WITH THINGS IDLENESS THROUGH INTERACTION DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the conceptual object series *Living with Things*: seven working prototypes of electronically and mechanically altered everyday objects that explore emotional engagement through interaction design. It outlines aim, design and the interaction design model that was developed and applied. Further it looks at scenarios and experiences from the objects in use and finally places them in the larger context of my current PhD research into *The Design of Idleness*. This research looks at social acceleration from a design perspective and investigates the paradoxical potential of interaction design to contribute to the much-needed social and societal slowdown.

Keywords: interaction design, design activism, social acceleration, slow, idleness

INTRODUCTION

Living with Things is a conceptual design project. The original concern was to create objects that provide contemplation and comfort for the lost, lonely and stressed. A kind of cure for members of achievement-oriented societies, caught in the capitalist logic of growth of any kind. Instead of a superior authority, individuals in such systems are pushing and exploiting themselves in search for social and professional recognition, happiness or simply to not 'fall behind'. More and more they are struggling with symptoms and illnesses such as anxiety, depression, Burnout, borderline syndrome etc. In current debate across various disciplines those symptoms are considered implications of the underlying excessive work ethic and the spirit of capitalism (Weber 2003, Ehrenberg 2004, Rosa 2005, Han 2010). They are based on the disturbed

relationship between man and the world (of objects and subjects) going back to Marx's concepts of estrangement or alienation (1844). The aim was to contrive a conceptual piece of design as a momentum against feelings of alienation and acceleration by creating responsive and contemplative situations and connections, where usually the world seems mute and unresponsive. The intended experience outcome was to be a positive mental state, similar to the idea of flow, when one is completely and contentedly involved in an activity for its own sake. According to Csikszentmihalyi (1990), this ability to feel 'at one' with the present is the key to happiness and wellbeing. As people are in contact with tools and objects constantly in their everyday, it seemed obvious to begin there: using and re-interpreting everyday objects to induce responsive and slow actions and situations. The emerging objects were not meant to replace 'normal' household appliances, rather they should be used as needed – like medicine – or as psychological 'training equipment' for slowness.

DESIGN CONTEXT

CRITICAL & AWARENESS DESIGN

Conceptual objects, initially as art, were introduced by the Surrealists in the early 20th century with the everyday material finding its way into art practice, causing fruitful friction between the Known and Unknown. Over the last decade a similar experimental and artistic approach has been applied to design research to raise awareness, ask questions and stimulate discussion amongst designers, the industry and the public about the social, cultural and ethical implications of emerging technologies. Dunne and Raby's Critical Design or *Design for Debate* approach (1999, 2001) was passionately taken over and followed by many young designers, design

researchers and educators. A related field, similar in that it rejects design as problem-solving activity is Awareness Design. It considers design as exploratory activity that can augment life in poetic and aesthetic ways. In both approaches, a widely discussed and applied technique is ambiguity in design: creating ambiguous, 'open' designs and situations (Gaver 2002, 2003a, 2003b). Ambiguity in design facilitates reflection hence personal involvement. One 'has to make sense' of an artifact. *Living with Things* uses this method of interpretative appropriation along with responsive behavior as a promising 'cure' for alienation.

DESIGN ACTIVISM & SLOW DESIGN

Living with Things is a form of Design Activism. The term Design Activism describes proactive design that is not driven by economic and market values and that challenges the current role and aims of design and design practice. By definition Design Activism searches for possibilities how design can be a catalyst for positive social and ecological change (Fuad-Luke 2009). This places the work at hand into the larger context of social responsible design going back to Victor Papanek's Design for the real world (1971). *Living with Things* directly addresses social values and social change. Ecological change is implied, but not directly challenged. It is embodied in the values this work represents and in general by addressing the over-consumer society with an agenda for behavioral change.

Living with Things has been referenced in the context of Slow Design. The aim of Slow Design, with roots in the Slow Movement (Slow Food, Slow City, etc.), is a holistic design approach targeting ecological, social and individual wellbeing. So far, five design principles have been defined (Fuad-Luke and Strauss 2008): *Reveal, Expand, Reflect, Engage, Evolve*. The authors consider *Living with Things* as illustration of the evolve-principle: richer experiences can emerge from the dynamic maturation of artifacts and environments over time. Looking beyond the needs and circumstances of the present day, slow design artifacts become (behavioral) change agents.

While I feel comfortable with this broad classification,

I would like to keep the agenda of the work at hand tighter and focused on the psychological and emotional sufferings as side effects of social acceleration in modern societies and the search for strategies against those sufferings by reducing speed and the feeling of alienation in everyday life.

INTERACTION DESIGN MODEL

PART 1: EMOTIONAL ENGAGEMENT

The interaction technique that was developed and deployed for this work is based on the strong rejection of the Cartesian separation of mind and body on which most of the traditional philosophical approaches are based. I believe that emotional engagement (with an artefact, a person, myself) can be triggered by physical engagement. A recent related theory is Shusterman's concept of Somaesthetics (2008): aesthetic experience through body consciousness. The second crucial aspect to trigger emotional engagement draws on Norman's *Emotional Design* (2003). The objects evoke an urge to care and nurse them.

In practice, a part of each object's functionality has been removed. The function remains widely the same, the functionality is modified and limited. This missing link has to and can be easily replaced by the user (e.g. removing the headphones' head-strap, so the shells have to be manually held up, creating physical contact between object and user. See also fig. 3). Now, while 'using' the object one is at the same time supporting or 'helping' it (a nice gesture considering that usually objects around us simply 'serve' as tools without getting much credit or attention). In a subtle and intuitive way people are urged to engage with the objects physically. They find themselves in a symbiotic, reciprocal and friendly relationship.

PART 2: IDLENESS THROUGH INTERACTION DESIGN

The second part of the interaction design model is the induced incapacity to multi-task when using the objects. Because of the physical engagement, one is constrained to focus on the task at hand (e.g. listening to music while sending text messages becomes physically impossible). It is known that when it comes to attention the human brain, like computer

processors, cannot run more than one process at the time. Thus the thing called multitasking in reality is a fast switching from one process to another. Research has shown that this causes stress, reduces attention and multitaskers eventually produce noticeably poorer quality in what they do (e.g. Brasel and Gips 2011).

Being subtly pushed into a restrictive and exclusive action, all attention is focussed in the here and now and overall mindfulness increases. Related to mindfulness therapy, in particular as in mindfulness based stress reduction, feelings of calm- and slowness can emerge (e.g. Segal et al. 2001). Slowness – or Idleness here is considered something very worth achieving, essential for human health and creativity. Idleness surely is lacking in modern everyday life and wrongly has a poor reputation in our society. I will return to this topic at the end of this paper, when I situate this project in the context of my PhD research.

THE OBJECTS

The series encompasses seven working prototypes: lamp, umbrella, headphones, alarm clock, compass, metronome and radio (see fig. 1 and 2). Compass, metronome and radio are electronically enhanced using micro-controllers and various sensors and actuators; lamp, umbrella, headphones and alarm clock are mechanically altered. Not limiting the series to electronic objects was important to illustrate that the interaction model can be applied and is valid across different genres of objects, e. g. electronic and mechanic ones.

1. The lamp

A lamp without the usual stability. Technically still working, but the joints are loose: the lampshade has to be held manually.

2. The umbrella

The umbrella's inside supporting frame has been removed. It is now clinging to it's owner, who can hide under it.

3. The headphones

Bulky headphones, with the head-strap removed. To listen to music the shells have to be held by the user.

4. alarm clock

The alarm cannot be set to a particular time anymore. To make it ring, the chain replacing the alarm-button needs to be pulled: waking oneself up.

5. The compass

A compass in a small nautical wooden box. When opened, the compass needle starts searching and finds the person holding it instead finding North.

6. The metronome

The metronome does not set the beat anymore. Instead, the pendulum follows the movement of the person in-front of it.

7. The radio

The radio has no switch to turn it on. To make it start play, it needs to be held and carried around. Left alone, it stops playing.

Figure 1. Implementation examples.

Metronome (top): due to a custom-made, etched circuit board all electronics fit into a small box and can be hidden inside the object's base. Outside, left and right to the body infrared sensors are attached to track the occurring movement in-front of the object. Accordingly, the mechanic pendulum movement inside is interrupted and resumed via a micro-controller and electro-magnets.

Compass (below): the compass needle is controlled via a micro-controller and a weak electro-magnet inside the box. When the box is opened the magnet is switched on with a small time delay and draws the compass needle towards the front of the box. As the box always has to be held in a particular way to be opened, the position and alignment of the person holding the object is always known.

Figure 2. 'Subjectified' Objects

Documentary photographs showing the objects in use. The photographs accompany the physical objects in exhibition contexts. They are an integral part of the series. As actually using the objects requires a high level of intimacy, which can rarely be provided in exhibition contexts, the photographs are telling the very personal and intimate stories instead and serve as a platform or canvas for projecting one's own thoughts and emotions. From top-left to bottom-right:

1. Using the headphones creates a sensuous, self-aware moment. The very physical pose suggests an intimate, one-with-yourself moment.
2. Playful engagement with the metronome.
3. Alarm clock: only oneself is allowed to wake oneself up.
4. Holding the lamp during drawing. Warming one's hands and enjoying the flexibility to play with moving light and shadow on the paper.
5. Embracing the radio to make it play.
6. Hiding under the umbrella.

EXPERIENCES

EXPOSURE

Originally emerged as a conceptual design project, a conventional user evaluation has not been envisaged or conducted. The work has been shown in various exhibitions: sometimes *Things* and photographs together, sometimes just the photographs, as they are

substantially easier to handle and to display than electronic and delicate mechanic prototypes. Objects without the photographs have not been exhibited. When the objects were on display, the audience was free to engage with them. The exhibition context usually lacks intimacy, therefore the photographs – tracing the intimate moments between human and objects – are an essential supplement.

Since the emergence of *Living with Things* informal conversations about the work in and outside those exhibitions took place. Those reflections and discussions were a valuable and inspiring source of input. Some of my assumptions were confirmed and some new impulses for future work were given. A second valuable source for experiences and feedback were the photo-shootings. They developed into small 'workshops' each. For every object a full day at the model's home was spent, thinking through and inventing scenarios together with the model – respectively the object's owner for the day.

FEEDBACK

Motivation for using the objects – people would rather say they *played* (with) them – varied from curiosity, playfulness to suspiciousness or mistrust. As expected individual ways of interacting with them emerged, individual places where people would keep the *Things* were chosen (e.g. bring them to the office instead of keeping them at home). Most inspiring was how people described and called the objects. They considered them *needing creatures* or *little friends*, *things you have to look after, like children*. Using the objects felt like *play rather than doing something that is necessary*, even if it was necessary at that particular moment (e.g. needing light for drawing). There generally was a lot of positive and emotional feedback. Though people rarely could imagine replacing a 'normal' object with one of the *Things* in their home, they were very open and interested in the ideas behind them. Some said they would look at their things at home differently now, also at routinized actions. In general *Living with Things* triggered and raised a lot of positive mindfulness.

As also foreseeable some people strongly questioned the object's usefulness at large, even as a conceptual piece of work. Also there was frustration over *broken*, and *not working* objects, even if they were 'working' as intended by me as the author. I also experienced – rather rarely but evidently – total lack of understanding and empathy for the work. This reminds of how much the work draws on my personal cultural background and my social and philosophical education. It therefore can only be one in various approaches towards the social, psychological and societal effects that were aimed for with this work.

Obviously different personalities would require different interaction models. I was encouraged to keep those aspects and experiences in mind and later use them as the starting point for a more complex and daily use suitable model towards designing responsive experiences for social deceleration and idleness.

FUTURE RESEARCH

As described earlier, the ideas and aims behind *Living with Things* came to be the starting point for my current PhD research into *The Design of Idleness*. This research looks at social acceleration (Rosa 2005) from a design perspective and investigates the potential of interaction design to contribute to the much-needed social and societal slowdown. This seems to be a paradoxical endeavor as design usually acts as catalyst for growth and increased efficiency rather than for deceleration. This reverse role for design, so argues this research, is urgently needed in western achievement-oriented societies. Design is attributed a paradigmatic role for the 21st century (Mau 2004, Fuad-Luke 2009) and as in the tidal waves of the 2008 financial and the following economic crisis it now is widely considered common sense that we drastically have to change not only our behavior and way of living, but first of all our values and understanding of what we consider a good life. If design has the potential to play a paradigmatic role as a discipline – which I believe – values in design too (or prior) have to change.

Idleness in this context is regarded one of those (old) new values and has to be re-established in society and liberated from the negative notion of simple passiveness and sloth. Introducing idleness back into our everyday life is not only essential for mental and physical health (Ehrenberg 2004, Han 2010), it is also the premise for social participation by providing space for reflection: creative, fertile idleness in the vivid sense ancient greek philosophers used and lived it.

My current research considers interaction design as appropriate tool to introduce idleness into everyday life. Related frameworks such as the Slow Design principles mentioned earlier or the Slow Technology approach (Hallnäs and Redström 2001) will be taken

into account as well as research on busyness and productivity (e.g. Leshed and Sengers 2011). Enforced idleness and restrictive actions as utilized in *Living with Things* is only a first step towards a more complex and suitable for daily use model of *idleness through design*.

To develop and apply this model through and in empirical design experiments is the aim of my PhD research. With emphasis on design practice in the research process – encompassing analysis, projection and synthesis in an iterative circle – it is a contribution to the model of Research Through Design (Jonas 2007). As the research topic will – hopefully in fruitful ways – accompany me for a long time in my future practice, the PhD research will presumably be completed in 2014.

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Online project documentation for *Living with Things* is available at: www.livingwiththings.org

The future research process of *The Design of Idleness* will be available at: www.monikahoinkis.de/research

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